

GPP STANDARD OF MODERN UZBEKISTAN PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS

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One of the issues discussed was the implementation of compliance with the GPP standard for pharmacy organizations (Good Pharmacy Practice). This standard, along with increasing the role of the pharmacist in society, will change the essence of the sale of medicines and the quality of pharmaceutical services provided. The implementation and strict adherence to the standard will be a key point in improving the healthcare system and helping to improve the level of health in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Also, the implementation of the GPP standard for pharmacy organizations in the Republic of Uzbekistan and its impact on the quality of pharmaceutical services. The implementation of this standard will help improve the healthcare system and improve the level of public health. GPP, the emphasis during testing is on three points: the procedure for taking medications, storage conditions and pharmaceutical advice.

Purpose of the study: To consider the current state of pharmacies and their branches in order to implement the requirements of the standard and obtain a GPP certificate.

Materials and methods of research: study of literature and documents on the research topic, analysis of the information obtained, observation, analysis and generalization of the activities of the pharmacy.

Key words: GPP, standardization, certificate, SOP, good practice.

Research result: The main principle of GPP is this: everything that is done in a pharmacy must be perfectly documented. Therefore, standards must be developed for each operating procedure, which clearly indicate what kind of procedure it is, on the basis of what regulatory documents it is carried out, where exactly, by which employee and for how long. This is a detailed algorithm that reflects all the circumstances of the action. Corresponding changes should also be made to the job descriptions of pharmacy workers. One of the most important requirements of good pharmacy practice is the need to inform customers about the range of drugs, starting with the cheapest segment. Disadvantages and ensuring full compliance with the requirements of the GPP standard, the following recommendations were made: 1. Develop and implement Quality Manual and Standard Operating Procedures (SOP) for the pharmacy. This will allow individual processes to be documented and the relationships between them to be defined in the form of SOPs. One of the important aspects is to inform customers about available medicines, starting with the most accessible segment.

Conclusions: The introduction of GPP will help reduce the risk of counterfeit and counterfeit medicines on the market. Thanks to strict regulations and requirements, pharmaceutical organizations will be required to monitor the quality and authenticity of medicines. In addition, the transition to the National Standard of Good Pharmacy Practice will help increase public confidence in pharmaceutical organizations. Patients will know that they are receiving high-quality and safe medicines, which will reduce the risk of unwanted side effects and complications. It contributes to raising the standards of pharmaceutical practice and improving public access to quality medicines.

Reference

Gulomovna B., Komilova N. CLEFT LIP AND PALATE //Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 12. – С. 7-11.

Gulomovna B., Salimov S., Urokov K. ANATOMY OF THE HUMAN SKULL
//Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №.
12. – С. 209-216.

Uchkunov S., Mamadaliyev J., Djuraeva B. EYE DISEASES IN MEDICINE
//Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №.
1 Part 2. – С. 128-135.